

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO TEACH CHILDREN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of this study is due to the fact that the introduction of new technologies in teaching foreign languages is one of the most important teacher tools that can help create not only a memorable lesson, but also an experience that will remain with children for a long time. The hypothesis of the study suggests that the use of target and project methods in teaching foreign languages can make the most of the language resources of children, allowing them to diversify their own learning. With the advent of information technology and related devices, the role of the teacher has changed significantly.

INTRODUCTION

Youth mobility is a phenomenon that has probably always existed, but has come to the fore in the 21st century. Young people are interested in the world as a whole and are ready to travel and expand their horizons. The first reason for youth mobility is naturally the desire for adventure, the desire to see new cities and countries and acquire new experiences. Without knowledge of foreign languages, this is quite problematic¹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Currently, domestic education follows the principle of variability - it provides teachers of foreign languages with the opportunity to independently choose teaching methods, use innovative teaching models, author's courses, interactive methods aimed at developing the student's personality, his effective social adaptation, "implantation" in a foreign language culture.

Among the many new pedagogical technologies, the following are used more often than others: cooperative learning; project method; multi-level training; individual and differentiated approach to learning.

Task-based learning. With this method of teaching foreign languages, the central direction of the lesson is the task itself, and not the grammatical point or lexical area, and the goal is not to "learn the structure", but to "complete the task". Of course, in order to successfully complete the task, children must use the necessary language tools and convey their ideas. Therefore,

¹ Zimnyaya I.A. Psychological aspects of teaching speaking in a foreign language. - M., 2011. - 222 p.

the language becomes a communication tool, the purpose of which is to help in the successful completion of the task. There is usually no "correct answer" to achieve the outcome of a task.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is possible to use targeted learning in two ways: integrate it into an existing curriculum (or use it to replace the curriculum as a whole) and apply it as an "additional" to traditional classroom activities².

The tasks of the target method of teaching foreign languages are divided into three stages.

Stage 1: preliminary task. The teacher introduces the topic and introduces children to situations / lexical areas / texts (reading and listening). This draws attention of children to the topic. The trainer offers lexical material that may be useful. Then the teacher explains what the task is and sets them up for activity.

Stage 2: Children complete the task in pairs or groups. They can then present their findings to the rest of the group. At this stage, the mistakes are not important, the teacher provides support and monitors all the lexical and grammatical aspects of the utterance. Children are focused on communication, perhaps at the expense of language accuracy, but this will be addressed in the next step.

Stage 3: the teacher works on the specific language items that appeared in the previous stage. Children reflect on the language tools needed to complete the task. This is an opportunity to focus on linguistic accuracy and make sure they are able to solve any problems and overcome any doubts. Whatever the task, it must always have a logical conclusion, focused on the "class-language", which naturally follows from the task, and not vice versa.

Project based learning. This method takes student-centeredness to a higher level. It shares many aspects of targeted learning, but is even more ambitious. While targeted learning puts the task at the forefront only in the lesson, project-based learning often puts the task in the center of attention for the entire duration of the training or for the academic year³.

It is used as the basis for a whole year's work, or it can be devoted to a certain amount of time along with the curriculum. It is allowed to use project-based learning only for short-term, or "intensive" courses.

The authors of the study considered four elements that are common to all project-based activities:

- the main theme from which all activities flow and which drives the project to achieve the final goal;
- access to learning tools (the Internet has greatly facilitated this part of the project work) for the collection, analysis and use of information;
- many opportunities for exchanging ideas, collaborating and communicating – interaction with other learners is fundamental to project-based learning;
- the final product (often produced using new technologies available to us) in the form of posters, presentations, reports, videos, web pages, blogs, and so on.

The roles of the teacher and the learner in the project-based learning approach are very similar to those in the goal-based learning approach. Children are given the freedom to solve problems and share information. The teacher's role is to monitor and facilitate, create a

² Kolker Ya.M. Practical method of teaching a foreign language. - M., 2010.

³ Passov E.I. Communicative method of teaching foreign language speaking. - M., 2015. - 208 p.

framework for communication, provide access to information and help with language where needed, and enable children to prepare the final product or presentation. As with targeted learning, the trainer controls the interaction, but does not interrupt it due to the presence of language errors.

In the project and targeted teaching of foreign languages, elements of a creative approach were also involved, representing creativity as one of the many innate skills and abilities that every person and every language learner has. This approach focuses on the idea that we can all use our inherent potential to be creative under certain conditions; that we all abound in different forms and levels of creativity, and that the task of the teacher is to stimulate creativity in children.

In the teaching of foreign languages, there is also a positive trend in the active use of new forms of organization of the educational process. Educational Internet portals in foreign languages are being created, computer classes are being opened. In the classroom, video materials are used, electronic textbooks are used, virtual tours and video conferences are held. Foreign language teachers are increasingly using project methods with the involvement of computer technology⁴.

The advantages of using the global Internet with the proper organization of classroom and extracurricular work of students are obvious:

- provides access to huge volumes of constantly updated authentic media texts;
- the possibility of real oral and written communication with native speakers is provided and the skills of a culture of interethnic communication are developed;
- solving a number of didactic tasks is facilitated (the vocabulary of students is expanding, writing skills are improving, etc.);
- the general outlook of students is expanding and a stable motivation for learning foreign languages is formed;
- a student-centered approach to learning is being implemented;
- independent cognitive activity of students is activated and the foundations of research work are laid.

CONCLUSION

Foreign language teachers have three advantages that can help stimulate pupil-student creativity⁵:

– firstly, language is creative by nature. We can express or convey a thought in a variety of forms. In addition, anyone who has expressed a thought or message can elicit many different reactions. Every sentence, phrase, or word we speak or write is created in a unique moment of communication and can be recreated, reworded, paraphrased, or altered for purpose orally and in writing;

– secondly, language classes are not limited to any specialized subject or knowledge. Therefore, language teachers can build their classes around sports, management, law or philosophy and still focus on the language. In a practical session, children and teachers can easily establish a relationship in which they share their individual knowledge and experience;

⁴ Novikova A.A. Media education in English classes. Taganrog, 2014.P.34.

⁵ Borisova I.I., Livanova E.Yu. Interactive forms and methods of teaching in higher education: Proc. allowance. – N. Novgorod: Nizhny Novgorod State University. N.I. Lobachevsky (NNSU), 2011. - 65 p.

- thirdly, language classes can easily involve children in creative situations. By creative situations, we mean situations that are close to reality, in which children do not just use well-known and proven elements and apply them almost automatically to achieve one correct solution to a problem. In creative situations, children must provide one or more answers to a series of interrelated questions. They don't know what steps can be taken to solve the problem. They cannot know for sure whether a problem has one solution, a wide range of possible solutions, or whether it has any solution at all. Children simply do not face clear-cut situations that can only lead to "success-failure" or "right-wrong" decisions, they face problem situations that do not have unambiguous solutions. Sometimes even the setting of a situation or instructions may require a certain level of interpretation. Since the use of language is a form of communication that can be used in almost any situation, authenticity or a real life situation can be created much more easily than in other areas of training.

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